

Self-Concept, Interpersonal Relationship and Anger Management of City Transport and Traffic Management Office Personnel in Davao City

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Abstract:- The study aimed to determine the influence of self-concept and interpersonal relationship on anger management among City Transport and Traffic Management Office (CTTMO) personnel in Davao City, Philippines. This research study used a quantitative, descriptive, non-experimental, and correlational research. The respondents of the study were the randomly selected 300 CTTMO personnel of Davao City in 2021. In choosing the respondents, this study employed a random sampling technique. The researcher utilized face to face survey. Mean, Pearson r, and Regression were the statistical tools employed in the study. Results showed that the levels of self-concept, interpersonal relationship, and anger management were all high. Findings further revealed that both self-concept and interpersonal relationship positively correlate with anger management, however, only interpersonal relationship showed a significant influence on anger management. Hence, it is recommended that CTTMO personnel may be exposed to further trainings on enhancing their interpersonal relationship in order to attain a very high level of anger management which is considered vital in disposing their duties and responsibilities.

Keywords:- criminal justice, self-concept, interpersonal relationship, anger management, city transport and traffic management office personnel, Davao city, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Anger is a bad emotion that may be controlled positively. Anger is a learned habit (Maslach, 2017). The majority of rage-related issues stem from improper expression of anger, yet the importance of adequate expression is still questioned. Among the most essential points to note about rage is that it is a normal emotion. So, fury is something that cannot be ignored. When anger becomes uncontrolled and destructive, it causes enormous issues in work, personal relationships, and general quality of life (Velmurugan, 2016). In addition, not expressing rage adequately depletes strength and makes it harder to manage behavior (Baran, 2019). Anger, from the other hand, may hurt the man and his surroundings if not controlled. So, it has pleasant and unpleasant functions (Soyka, 2017).

A rapid growth in the number of crimes committed by youth, widespread abuse in families, racial tensions, an increase in terrorist attacks, and the involvement of ordinary individuals around the world all indicate that anger is at the

heart of many of the problems facing people in today's human life era. Despite this, rage disorders are not addressed or categorized in any diagnostic categorization system or treatment plan for anger management (Erckon, 2017).

The increase in the number of references to the term "anger management" in scientific databases demonstrates the prominence of this topic. Apart from this, the large number of methods of anger management and control point to the increasing significance of anger avoidance, as well as the use of rational and wise strategies, which are distancing from the basic emotional systems of the brain's old structures and are considered as neocortical methods of today's world (Liven, 2017). Although there are few comparison studies on impact size, preference, and priority rate as well as the application of different anger management approaches, typically in the case of review articles, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses, there is a growing body of comparative research.

Due to demands in the work, many employees exert enormous amount of pressure to ensure a smooth operation and achieved the desired goal. This continuous pressure would eventually take a toll on them and can often lead to chronic stress and anger in any circumstance (Huang, 2016), which then can cause psychological, emotional, physical and behavioral problems among employees and affects their overall well-being especially their interpersonal relationships (Borritz, 2016). Several studies provide emphasis on the problem about anger management that impacts the interpersonal relationship of the employees. In fact, nearly three-quarters of American workers surveyed in 2012 reported experiencing unmanageable anger as a result of stress in work (Lapan, 2017).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter deals with the methods and processes for the conduct of the study. It aims to present the Study participant/ research subject, materials/instruments, design and procedure of the study.

The respondents of the study were the CTTMO officers of Davao City year 2021. The following populations of every section of the department were as follows: Traffic Enforcer 265, Traffic Aide 387, Special Operation Team 22, Cycle Unit 30, Jay Walking 37, Mobile Unit 57, Office Staff 33 and the total number of employees are 831.

The stratified, random selection strategy was used in this research to choose the participants for participation. This

is a sampling technique that includes separating a society into smaller groups, which are referred to as strata. The members of the group are grouped into groups or strata depending on the traits or features that they have in common with one another. Stratification is the process of dividing a population into groups and assigning them names.

The study, which focused on self-concept, interpersonal relationship, and anger management excluded from the study are the CTTMO employees who are retired, discharged, or awol in the service. Respondents who refuse to participate in the survey are granted the choice to do so without risking any consequences, penalties, or loss of benefits under the withdrawal criteria.

The research was carried out in the city of Davao. In terms of land size, it covers a total area approximately 2,443.61 km² (943.48 sq mi), which makes it the biggest city in the Philippines throughout terms of land area. It is the third-most populated city in the Philippines, behind Quezon City and Manila, and the most populous city in the province of Mindanao, according to the 2010 census. The city will have a total population of 1,825,450 people by 2020. Even though it is physically located inside the province of Davao del Sur and is classified as portion of the province by the Philippine Statistics Authority, the city is governed and managed separately from the rest of the province. The city is split into three congressional districts, each of which is further subdivided into 11 administrative districts, with a total of 182 barangays. The city is divided into 3 congressional districts, each of which is further subdivided into 11 administrative districts. Davao City is the

administrative hub of Metro Davao, which is the Philippines' third-most populated metropolitan region. (According to the 2015 census, the population of this area was 2.5 million, compared to the 12.8 million of Metro Manila and the 2.8 million of Metro Cebu.) The city acts as the central trade, business, and industrial core of Mindanao, as well as the regional capital of the Davao Region, according to the United Nations Development Programme. Mountains such as Mount Apo, the Philippines' tallest peak, may be found near Davao. Additionally, the city is known as the "Durian Capital of the Philippines" as well as the "Chocolate Capital of the Philippines."

This study utilized an adapted-modified questionnaire. This is the main tool that will be used in gathering the data needed for the study. It was designed according to the variables reflected in this study. The first part of the adopted questionnaire determines the level of self-concept among CTTMO officers in terms of physical, moral-ethical, personal, family, and social. This was adapted from the study of Marsh (1987). It has the Cronbach alpha of 0.81 which was highly reliable. The first independent variable, transformational leadership, was measured utilizing questions adapted from (Campbell, 2011) It contained seven indicators namely: Individualized consideration, Encourage the heart, Inspirational motivation, Intellectual stimulation, Challenge the process, make it possible for others to function as models for you. The following replies been made available to the respondents:

Meanwhile, the questionnaire was rated by the respondents from 5 as the highest score and 1 as the lowest score. Such range had its respective descriptive equivalent and interpretation. The data was interpreted using the table below, which has a 5-point Likert - type scale to evaluate its degree of significance.

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Self-concept is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Self-concept is often manifested.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	Self-concept is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	Self-concept is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Self-concept is never manifested.

Secondly, another part of the questionnaire measures the level of interpersonal relationship among CTTMO officers in terms of trust, self-disclosure, genuineness, empathy, comfort, and communication which was also adapted from the study of Henry (1998). It has the Cronbach alpha of 0.76 which was reliable.

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Interpersonal relationship is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Interpersonal relationships often manifested.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	Interpersonal relationship is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	Interpersonal relationship is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Interpersonal relationship is never manifested.

Furthermore, the third part determines the anger management among CTTMO officers enumerated as escalating strategies, calming strategies, negative attribution, and self-awareness. This questionnaire was adopted from the study of Stith (2002). It has the Cronbach alpha of 0.80 which was reliable.

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	Anger managementis always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	Anger managementis often manifested.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	Anger managementis sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	Anger managementis seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Anger managementis never manifested.

This research study used a quantitative descriptive correlational research design. Quantitative research approach is concerned with numbers and everything that can be measured in a systematic fashion in order to investigate phenomena and the links between them. It is used to provide answers to queries about connections between observable variables with the goal of explaining, predicting, and controlling a phenomenon (Leedy, 2016).

In most cases, the conclusion of a quantitative research is either confirmation or issues of self of the theory that was examined. Quantitative researchers choose one or a few elements that they want to employ in their study effort and then begin collecting data on all those categories (Drake, 2012).

The process of measurement, according to Scalford (2013), lies at the heart of the quantitative approach, owing to the close connection that exists between empirical evidence and the mathematical formulation of quantitative relationships. This technique, also known as an iterative process, is characterized by the evaluation of evidence, the refinement of hypotheses and theories, and the use of statistical approaches to improve hypotheses and theories. The quantitative approach is often initiated by data collecting based on such a hypothesis or theory, and it is then followed by the implementation of descriptive and correlational statistics to the data.

With this, the study utilized a descriptive-correlation method in securing data to come up with the accurate result of the study. In research, a descriptive-correlation study is a strategy that explains and forecasts how variables are naturally connected in the actual world, without the researcher making any effort to modify the variables or attribute cause to the relationships between variables (Frat, 2015).

The connection between the two (or more) factors is investigated using this approach, according to Shuttleworth (2014). Furthermore, Fernandez (2014) points out that research approach is also known as associational research, which lends credence to this claim. There are correlations between multiple variables that are investigated without making any effort to change the variables in question. This analyzes the potential of a link between two variables between the two variables are This research also does not include any manipulation of factors (Smiley, 2011).

Coordination study studies one or more qualities of a group in order to determine the degree to which the traits fluctuate in relation to one another. Research studies such as correlation research studies explore parameters in their natural surroundings without the use of experimental treatments imposed by the researchers (Simon, 2011). By using methods such as cross-tabulation and correlations, correlational investigations are able to demonstrate the links between variables.

Ex post facto studies, also known as correlational studies, are investigations that are conducted after the event. To put it another way, this literally means "after the event." Typically, the word is used to indicate that the study has been carried out after the phenomena of interest has happened in the wild. The primary goal of a correlational research is to identify whether or not there is a link amongst variables, and if there is, to develop a regression model that may be used to predict future about a group of individuals (Simon, 2011).

The researcher hopes to find out whether there is a link between passion management and self-concept, as well as between intensive therapy and interpersonal relationships, among CTTMO officers in this study. If there is a link between both variables of sufficient size, it becomes feasible to determine a score on one variable if a result from the other element is already known (Cummins, 2012).

In collecting the data, the following steps were undertaken. Firstly, the researcher asked the Professional Schools of the University of Mindanao a request letter to conduct study, to conduct survey using adapted modified questionnaires to the CTTMO personnel in Davao City and it was properly addressed to the head of office S/Supt. Dionisio C. Abude (Ret) Chief of the City Transport and Traffic Management Office personnel in Davao. After getting permit and approval the researcher automatically distributes survey questionnaires to the CTTMO personnel in their respective assigned area in Davao City.

Only after getting the approval from the targeted locales, the researcher conducted the survey to qualified respondents based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The researcher personally administered the survey instruments during the respondents agreed time. This was done to ensure that the researcher would not be able to disrupt their working time. However, certain challenges were experienced by the researcher in data gathering especially during pandemic. There were the following: having respondents who were not really keen to participate, where to locate possible respondents, how to persuade them to participate, and then making them comfortable to talk in

complete surveys. More specific challenges occur when the researcher had a lack of experience conducting quantitative studies.

A researcher had also some difficulties and challenges on how to choose participants, and also when seeking to establish rapport with respondents during the data gathering, who are unlike them. The researcher also came across respondents who were resistant to participate in the data gathering based on concerns about the confidentiality of their information.

A. Self-Concept

The data analysis and interpretation presented in this chapter are based on replies received from City Transport and Traffic Management Office (CTTMO) workers in Davao City and are presented in this chapter. The presentations are broken down into two sections. It is divided into three parts: part one deals with the suitable point of measures, which are organized under the categories level of self-concept, part two deals with interpersonal relationships, and part three deals with anger management. Describes the relevance of the link between each independent variable, such as personality and interpersonal interaction, and the outcome variable, anger management, in the second section.

The amount of Self-Concept expressed by City Transport and Traffic Management Office (CTTMO) workers in Davao City is shown in Table 1, which can be seen here. The total mean score was 3.74 with a variance of 0.185, which was classified as high, indicating that the CTTMO personnel's Self-Concept was often exhibited in their actions. This also suggested that the staff of the CTTMO had a positive self-concept.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Physical	0.192	3.69	High
Moral Ethical	0.233	3.56	High
Personal	0.224	3.55	High
Family	0.251	3.96	High
Social	0.224	3.95	High
Overall	0.185	3.74	High

Table 1: The level of Self-Concept

B. Interpersonal Leadership

The degree of interpersonal contact among CTTMO employees is shown in Table 2. In all, the mean rating is 3.51 with such a standard deviation of 0.244, which is classified as extremely high, indicating that interpersonal relationships were often demonstrated by members of the CTTMO staff. Additionally, this revealed that the CTTMO workers had a very high degree of interpersonal relationships with one another.

The following are the mean scores of the markers of interpersonal connection that were discovered: Comfort earned a total mean of 3.60 or high with a standard deviation of 0.306; consciousness received a mean rating of 3.53 or high with a standard deviation of 0.296; genuineness received an average score of 3.51 or high with a standard deviation of 0.328; communication received a mean rating of 3.50 or high with a standard deviation of 0.343; and trust received a mean

The following are the mean scores for the markers of self-concept reported by the study: Among the categories evaluated, family received a total mean of 3.96 or high with a mean difference of 0.225; social received a mean rating of 3.95 or high with just a standard deviation of 0.224; physical received a mean rating of 3.69 or high with such a standard deviation of 0.192; moral ethical received a weighted mean of 3.56 or high with a standard error of 0.233; and personal received an average score of 3.55 or high with either a standard deviation of 0.224.

The high level of Self-concept among CTTMO personnel is due to the high ratings given by the respondents on family, social, physical, personal and moral ethical indicators of Self-concept. The CTTMO personnel in Davao City oftentimes manifested Self-concept. Further, studies showed that CTTMO personnel possesses healthy body, and seeing good points on how people expect to see themselves in enforcing traffic laws and regulations to become more effective and observant at all times, to have an efficient traffic flow of vehicles and pedestrians. Enforcing laws fairly and honestly meets the good life satisfaction of all citizens as well as the commission officer of the CTTMO. The results are congruent to the proposition of (Berry 2019) introducing new policy, to improve officers' health as well as their self-concept, and consequently organizational performance. The police departments in England increase singly focus on shift works on sleep, nutrition, and physical activity. It was also suggested by Diener and Schwarz (2017) stated that the self-concept is equal to the good life satisfaction with life in a hedonic sense.

rating of 3.44 or high with a standard deviation of 0; and trust received.

CTTMO individuals have a very high degree of interpersonal relationships, which is shown in the high ratings provided by respondents for trust, self-disclosure, authenticity, empathy, comfort, and communication, among other characteristics. Further, studies showed that the CTTMO personnel must express deep and strong feelings to their workmates such as sharing and discussing their problems and feeling comfortable in expressing everything. Being satisfied with family relation and listening carefully to their workers can help them to solve their problem. The results of the research are consistent with the viewpoints of Xu and Burlison (2017), who found that personal support helps people deal with life transitions or challenges by meeting their specific requirements in the given scenario. Personal, social, and moral ideas are shared between persons

to benefit the individual and his or her societal growth (Turner, 2016). It was suggested by Luan (2017) that in order to enhance a personnel's interpersonal interaction, an individual must be reactive and embody notions such as escapism, emotional and palliative care, and the use of

evasion techniques. An important component of this connection is active bargaining among people, which implies that they must participate in socializing with others, problem solving with others, minimization of worries with others, and participating in physical activity with workmates or peers

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Trust	0.232	3.44	High
Self-Disclosure	0.296	3.53	High
Genuineness	0.328	3.51	High
Empathy	0.404	3.49	High
Comfort	0.306	3.60	High
Communication	0.343	3.50	High
Overall	0.244	3.51	Very High

Table 2: The Level of Interpersonal Relationship

C. Anger Management

The degree of anger control among CTTMO employees is shown in Table 3. It can be seen on the table that discipline received a weighted rating of 3.41 with an error margin of 0.282, which was considered high, indicating that intensive outpatient program was often displayed among CTTMO workers. This further reinforced the fact that CTTMO officers in Davao City are very adept at managing their fury.

As a result of the study, the following mean scores were discovered: escalating strategies scored 3.53 out of 5, which is high, with a variance of 0.381; calming strategies scored 3.43 out of 5, which is high, with an error margin of 0.222; negative attributes scored 3.35 out of 5, which is moderate, with a sampling error of 0.313; and self-awareness scored 3.32 out of 5, which is moderate, with a standard error of 0.218

The high degree of mood swings among CTTMO staff in Davao City may be attributed to the high ratings provided by respondents on escalation methods, calming strategies, negative traits, and self-awareness, among other factors, in the survey. Furthermore, studies have shown that CTTMO staff has the capacity to stay cool and not quickly get enraged towards his or her coworkers, as well as the aptitude to become accountable and conscious of the conduct that they displayed towards their coworkers, regardless of how upset they are. According to Tian (2019), an individual's overall impression of life, emotions, and dispositional features may all play a significant influence in anger management, and these findings are consistent with his or her viewpoints. The idea of affectivity is closely associated with anger management. Having a high level of positive affectivity is characterized by feelings of euphoria, pleasure in one's activities, joy, social time, and extraversion, while having a low level of positive affectivity is characterized by feelings of drowsiness, fatigue,

and lethargy, as well as feelings of loneliness (Yung, 2018). Pleasant occurrences are reported more often by persons who have strong positive affectivity, while negative affectivity is reported less frequently by those who have a low level of positive affectivity (Watson, Clark, & Tellegen, 2018). On the other side, high negative affectivity is connected with feelings of upheaval, arousal to arousal, nervousness, guilt, and tension, whereas low negative vibes are associated with feelings of serenity and relaxation. More specifically, (Spielberger, 1991; Ozer, 1994) noted that anger-out refers to the act of expressing one's feelings of rage. In contrast, anger control refers to the inclination to normally behave in a reasonable, calm, tolerant, and understanding way as well as the ability to keep one's emotions under control and to calm down. Additionally, human service workers such as traffic cops and instructors are not unfamiliar with the feeling of being enraged. Individuals whose employment include interacting with and helping others are more likely to experience emotions of failure and exhaustion (Waugh & Judd, 2018). Goleman's theory of mind states that Recognizing ourselves better, living at least with who we are, and proactively controlling our thinking, emotions, and actions all depend on our capacity to monitor our thoughts and feelings from one instant to the next. Furthermore, self-aware individuals tend to behave deliberately rather than mindlessly, to be in excellent psychological health, and to have a happy attitude on life, according to the author of the study. It also implies a larger depth of life experience, as well as a greater likelihood of being more empathetic toward oneself and others. For example, a difference is often made between temporal and dispositional consciousness (Brown & Ryan, 2017), which reflects the divergent methods used by cognitive scientists and personality psychologists, respectively, to understanding self.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Escalating Strategies	0.381	3.53	High
Calming Strategies	0.222	3.43	High
Negative Attributes	0.313	3.35	Moderate
Self-Awareness	0.281	3.32	Moderate
Overall	0.282	3.41	High

Table 3: The Level of Anger Management

D. Significance of the Relationship between the Self-Concept and Anger Management

Shown in Table 4 is the data on the correlation of the independent variable Self-Concept to the dependent variable Anger Management. The overall findings demonstrated that self-concept had a statistically significant association to anger management, with an overall R value of .607 and a p value of 0.000, indicating a level of significance less than 0.05. Physical indicator was associated to the predictor variables Anger Management with an overall r-value of 0.614 and a significance level of 0.05; hence, the correlation was significant. When the dependent variable Anger Management was linked with the moral ethical indicator, the findings revealed an overall r-value of 0.513 with a p-value of 0.05, indicating that the relationship was significant. When the explanatory variables Anger Management was linked with the personal indicator, the total r-value calculated was 0.621 with a p-value of 0.05, which was still statistically significant. When the independent variable Anger Management was associated with the dependent variable Family Indicator, the findings revealed a high r-value of 0.479 with a p-value of 0.05. Finally, when the independent variable Anger Management was associated with the dependent variable Social Indicator, the total r-value obtained was 0.280 with a p-value of 0.05; this was also statistically significant. This demonstrated that all probabilities indicated statistically significant associations.

As a result of the study, the total R value was 0.607, and the p value was 0.000, indicating that Anger Management is significantly related to Self-Concept, at the 0.05 level of significance, according to the findings. It was shown that when the indicator of anger management, escalation techniques, was connected to the predictor variables Self-Concept, the total correlation coefficient (r) was 0.643 (p=0.000), which is less than 0.05 and hence significant. When the indicator of anger management, calming tactics, was linked with the independent variable, Self-Concept, the total r-value was 0.500 with a p-value of 0.05, indicating that the relationship was significant. When the predictor variables

Self-Concept was linked with the negative imputation indicator of anger management, the total r-value was 0.557 with a p-value of 0.05, indicating that the relationship was significant. After everything was said and done, when the self-awareness indicator of emotional regulation was associated to the variable Self-Concept, the total correlation coefficient was 0.557 with a p value of 0.05; this was also statistically significant.

It was discovered in the present research that there is a statistically significant association between ego and anger management among CTTMO workers in Davao City. This means that CTTMO personnel’s Anger Management determines their Self-Concept which can be seen in the data in terms of singular state, indicators physical, moral ethical, personal, family, and social are significantly correlated to Anger Management.

The findings of this research are consistent with the findings of Biaggio (2018), who found that there is a direct link between one’s self-concept and the manifestation of rage. According to the previous results, increased individuals scored lower on soul than medium-arousal individuals, but not by a significant margin. He observed that people with poor self-concept scored significantly lower on anger-arousal when assessed by the California Psychological Scale than those with medium- or high-arousal when evaluated by the Novaco Anger Assessment and the Anger Self-Report (N = 150). Furthermore, according to Aydn (2016), people who trust their family and have excellent ties with them have been seen to ensure good social connections as well, which has been shown to have a significant influence on an individual’s ability to regulate his or her anger. The findings of the study are also consistent with those of Yesilyaprak (2016), who found that subconscious is quite considerable and that a dramatically enhanced number of hours is spent beyond the family to friends, which is an important step in socialization and may help with anger management. However, this does not imply that the individuals want to be apart from their households or to spend time alone with their thoughts.

Self-Concept	Anger Management				
	Escalating Strategies	Calming Strategies	Negative Attribution	Self- Awareness	Overall
Physical	.609* (0.000)	.590* (0.000)	.529* (0.000)	.588* (0.000)	.614* (0.000)
Moral Ethical	.519* (0.000)	.392* (0.000)	.506* (0.000)	.489* (0.000)	.513* (0.000)
Personal	.623* (0.000)	.535* (0.000)	.588* (0.000)	.570* (0.000)	.621* (0.000)
Family	.526* (0.000)	.403* (0.000)	.444* (0.000)	.406* (0.000)	.479* (0.000)
Social	.367* (0.000)	.162* (0.005)	.226* (0.000)	.255* (0.000)	.280* (0.000)
Overall	.643* (0.000)	.500* (0.000)	.557* (0.000)	.557* (0.000)	.607* (0.000)

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Self-Concept and Anger Management

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

E. Significance of the Relationship between the Interpersonal Relationship and Anger Management

Shown in table 5 with regards to the indicators of the predictor parameters Interpersonal Relationship. The result revealed that Interpersonal Relationship has a significant relationship to Anger Management with the overall r value of .847 and the p value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance, considered to be significant. It was observed that when trust as an indicator of interpersonal relationship was linked to the response parameters Anger Management, the overall r -value was 0.494 with $p < 0.05$; hence, significant. When self-disclosure was related to the regressand parameters Anger Management, results disclosed an overall r -value of 0.856 with $p < 0.05$; thus significant. When genuineness was related to the regressand parameters Anger Management, the overall r -value computed was 0.148 with $p < 0.05$, still significant. When empathy was associated to the criterion. Anger Management, results disclosed an overall r -value of 0.935 with $p < 0.05$; thus significant. When comfort was associated to the criterion. Anger Management, the overall r -value computed was 0.780 with $p < 0.05$, still significant. Finally, when communication was parallel to the criterion. Anger Management, the overall r -value obtained was 0.597 with $p < 0.05$; likewise, significant. This showed that all probability values signified significant correlations. On the other hand, when escalating strategies indicator of Anger Management was parallel to the covariate. Interpersonal Relationship, the overall r -value was 0.866 with $p < 0.05$; hence, significant. When calming strategies indicator of anger management was associated to the regressor variable Interpersonal Relationship, the overall r -value was .726 with $p < 0.05$; hence, significant. When negative attribution indicator of anger management was associated to the regressor variable Interpersonal Relationship, the overall r -value was .767 with $p < 0.05$; hence, significant. Finally, when self-awareness indicator of anger management was link to the covariate variable Interpersonal Relationship, the overall r -value was .800 with $p < 0.05$; likewise, significant.

The findings of the research were consistent with the findings of Amnihu (2018), who found that anger is related to interpersonal relationships and that interpersonal relationship types are important in anger manifestation. An participant's physically and mentally health are both negatively impacted by a prolonged state of rage, as is his or her ability to maintain healthy interpersonal relationships (Xian, 2020). The

relationship between anger expressive style and interpersonal issues was also investigated in a number of different groups, including students of the university, children, and people, among other things (Pian, 2017). The findings of this research are also consistent with those of Lahin (2017), who found that those who experienced interpersonal issues exhibited the least level of anger-control behavior. The suppressive anger-control group, on the other hand, had more interpersonal issues than the other groups, according to the results of the research. Human beings' emotions and expressive styles may be classified in a variety of ways, however there are limitations to this approach. To better understand the many types of anger expression styles, it is vital to categorize them into naturally existing groupings that can further take into consideration the qualities of each person (Abominar, 2017).

Furthermore, the findings of this study are consistent with the findings of Solliman (2018), who found that effective individual discipline has significant social and interpersonal effects for the individual. Furthermore, Rime (2017) states that a large number of well-known past research have established throughout time that periods of anger issues are often associated with long-term psychological and social repercussions and impacts. Individuals' emotional experiences often inspire and motivate them to engage in crucial social acts. Positive emotional regulation is associated with greater levels of social interaction quality (Lopes et al., 2016; Salovey et al., 2016; Côté et al., 2016; Beers et al., 2016). Furthermore, it has been proven that alternative emotional-anger control strategies—for example, reassessment vs suppression—lead to differing interpersonal outcomes and functional outcomes. When especially in comparison to suppression as an active coping approach (the repression or downregulation of expressed emotion), reappraisal as an emotion - focused coping strategy (i.e., organizing an individual's view of a negative heart situation in a way that shifts or needs changing its emotional weight) is related to better psychological relationships (Gross & John, 2016). Additionally, notions such as emotional intelligence, in which the ability to recognize and control one's emotions is critical, are linked to positive outcomes in interpersonal interactions. According to Schutte (2018), higher levels of emotional intelligence were associated with higher scores on social skills tests, greater inter-personal cooperation, and far more successful personal relations, specifically pretty close and more affectionate relationships, as well as higher levels of marital satisfaction scores.

Interpersonal Relationship	Anger Management				
	Escalating Strategies	Calming Strategies	Negative Attribution	Self- Awareness	Overall
Trust	.573* (0.000)	.417* (0.000)	.419* (0.000)	.419* (0.000)	.494* (0.000)
Self-Disclosure	.845* (0.000)	.688* (0.000)	.814* (0.000)	.844* (0.000)	.856* (0.000)
Genuineness	.064 (0.268)	.175* (0.002)	.138* (0.017)	.219* (0.000)	.148* (0.010)
Empathy	.964* (0.000)	.742* (0.000)	.912* (0.000)	.844* (0.000)	.935* (0.000)
Comfort	.768* (0.000)	.710* (0.000)	.687* (0.000)	.763* (0.000)	.780* (0.000)
Communication	.690* (0.000)	.542* (0.000)	.464* (0.000)	.513* (0.000)	.597* (0.000)
Overall	.866* (0.000)	.726* (0.000)	.767* (0.000)	.800* (0.000)	.847* (0.000)

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Interpersonal Relationship and Anger Management

*Significant at 0.05 significance level

F. The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Anger Management

Reflected in Table 6 is the extent of influence of predictor variables on Anger Management of CTTMO personnel. It can be extracted from the findings that the predictor variables Self-Concept and Interpersonal Relationship has a combined percent influence of 71.8% with an F ratio of 377.364. The total r-value of 0.847 with p<0.05 which is < 0.05 level of significance. The result revealed that all of the predictor variables were found to statistically explain the Anger Management of CTTMO personnel in Davao City.

Furthermore, CTTMO personnel have some degree of Anger Management and the R2 value of 0.718 shows that 71.8 % of the variance of Anger Management is contributed by the two independent variables namely, Self-Concept and Interpersonal Relationship. Data analysis shows 32.7% factors of alienation which denotes that there are other factors that influence Anger Management of CTTMO personnel apart from Self-Concept and Interpersonal Relationship which are not included in the present study. Moreover, data show the following t values of the independent variables, namely: Self-Concept, T value = -.667 with p = 0.505, hence, not significant (p>0.05); and Interpersonal Relationship T value = 19.168 with p = .000, hence, significant (p<0.05). From the result, only Interpersonal Relationship has the significant influence on Anger Management.

Prediction Equation Model:

$$Y_{AM} = 0.176 + 1.002X_{IR}$$

Where: Y_{AM} = Anger Management

X_{IR} = Interpersonal Relationship

This denotes that for every 1.002-unit increase in the level of Interpersonal Relationship there is a corresponding 1-unit increase in the level of Self-Concept.

The result of the study was congruent with the exploration of Hunna (2018) Self-Concept insignificantly relating to Anger Management. The study confirmed that behind passive aggressive and active aggressive behavior does not always relevant to low self-concept. People with low self-concept will sometimes just use anger when they feel like their opinions and feelings do not mean much. Moreover, feeling self-conscious, victimized or diminished in some way utilizes anger as a form of self-defense, however, it does not connect to self-concept itself.

On the other hand, Interpersonal Relationship predicts Anger Management. This is in line with the study of Loroa (2017) who indicated that interpersonal relationships are not only interiorized in the image of another person, but also exteriorized on the basis of such acts of anger, interaction, as reactions, actions and gestures, addressed to another individual and provoking his/her active reactions, actions and gestures, which become features, qualities, characteristics of a personality. As a result, an individual's mental and physical health, as well as his or her ability to control one's anger, are jeopardized by a protracted condition of poor interpersonal relationship

Anger Management (Dependent Variable)				
Independent Variables	B (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	t	Sig.
Constant	.063	.176	.360	.719
Self-Concept (SC)	-.030	-.046	-.667	.505
Interpersonal Relationship (IR)	.869	1.002	19.168	.000
R	.847			
R ²	.718			
F	377.364			
p	.000			

Table 6: The extent of Influence of Predictor Variables on Job Satisfaction

III. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This part contains the research's results and recommendations, which serve to synthesize what was suggested, debated, and completed during the course of the study. The following important conclusion was reached by the researcher as a result of the study findings.

Results showed that the levels of self-concept and anger management are all high while the level of interpersonal relationship is very high. Results also revealed that both self-concept and interpersonal relationship positively correlate with anger management, however, only interpersonal relationship revealed a significant influence predictor variable on anger management. Hence, it is recommended that CTTMO personnel may be exposed to trainings to enhance their interpersonal relations in order to attain a very high level of anger management which is considered vital in disposing their duties and responsibilities. This indicates that Anger Management of CTTMO personnel with indices escalating strategies, calming strategies, negative attribution, and self-awareness has something to do with Interpersonal Relationship. This is supported by the claim of Amnhu (2018), who said that anger is significant to interpersonal relationships and that trust and intimacy styles are critical in the expression of angry feelings. An individual's personal psychosomatic health are both negatively impacted by a prolonged state of rage, as is his or her ability to maintain healthy interpersonal relationships (Xian, 2020;).

The researcher made the following suggestions in light of the results as well as conclusion of the study that have already been mentioned.

It is recommended that City Traffic Transport Management Office personnel developed in terms of their self-concept in order to enhance the anger management among the CTTMO personnel in Davao City. Furthermore, results showed that interpersonal relationship was found out to be the predictor of anger management, therefore, training's may be conducted in order to enhance anger management of City Traffic Transport Management Office personnel.

Finally, it is recommended that extensive studies maybe be pursued among future researchers considering the variables of this study such self-concept and interpersonal relationship and anger management in realm of policing sectors since very few empirical studies were conducted.

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